

Generalization of Citation Style for Music

Arjun Dahal

Mental Asylum of Education

P.O. Box 1

Gauradaha, Jhapa

arjundahalard.thereason@gmail.com

Abstract:

Like as of MLA, APA, Chicago Manual, and various other types of citation styles, which can be found in across the world, in this paper author has attempted to provide a generalized way of citation style for music.

Introduction:

Referencing and citation styles are needed to provide bibliographic information source of resources/researches, that we do publish. Thus by considering readers well aware about specific citation styles that are used around the world, we shall attempt to provide an example of generalization of citation as:

Name of Song | Name of Movie/Album | Actors/Artists | Music (Musician) | Singer | Lyricist | Genre |
Format of song | Genre | Released Date.

Author has written by considering few music videos in Youtube, especially of Hindi Songs and Nepali Songs [1] [2] [3] [4], and couldn't found any proper generalization of citation styles. I don't know, if each companies producing music have their own way for citation, but generalized citation would be amazing. In one example [1] name of director (I don't know if it is same fellow in music too or not) can be found, and in another example [2], name of lyricist can't be found in title of song. Those two were examples to discuss about our proposed citation style, which doesn't include producers, and directors, and their entire team, leaving them for bibliographic records. Similarly for music, that are found in Albums, sang by a singer or entire band, same citation technique would be able to provide us with bibliographic reference.

For covered songs, that are sang by other peoples then the originals, our citation style becomes:

Name of song | Name of Movie/Album | Actors/Artists | Music (Musician) | Singer | Lyricist | Genre |
Format of song | Released Date | Covering Artist (Covered /Remade/Reworked by) | Released Date of
covered song.

Mentioning entire team in production would make citation style much lengthier, thus we did discussed with selected sections in citation style. In Bands, singers are generally called as frontman, and in our "Music" section in citation, we have attempted to provide name of Musician with greater contribution, as all fellows while making music do equally contribute for better music, and for music without videos, just name of artist especially mascot makers can be discussed, and other sections are defined as per Music industry.

Conclusion:

Citation Styles are important and citation style for music would allow entire music to be discussed in terms of bibliography, depending upon their publication/broadcasting/release on any platform, like author discussed about Youtube(A video publication site in Internet) as platform. That would make our study of Music more systematic when needed to cite for academic purposes.

Cons and Comments:

Citation style presented by author in this paper, would make title of music, as a style of citation. For our daily talks, and livelihood, just song is preferred, where as in academic sector citation style is needed, which author thought to write as cons.

References:

1. <https://youtu.be/WWXm39leYew> (Video in Youtube of Hindi Song, "Kaise Hua")
2. <https://youtu.be/Dp6lbdoprZ0> (Video in Youtube of Hindi song, "Mein Ragoon Ya Na Ragoon")
3. <https://youtu.be/ta07bMHe8Lk> (Video in Youtube of Nepali Song, "Teenpatey- Dekhera Timilaa")
4. <https://youtu.be/URzQtbwNmIs> (Video in Youtube of Nepali Song, "Fulbutte Saari")